

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4056, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:59:57
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	43,1	149µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	43,1	221µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4056, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:59:57
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	38,2	49,4µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	38,2	82,0µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4056, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:42:27
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	19,1	53,3	17,7µV	83,6µV
5 R-1	20,1	47,9	31,7µV	191µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	16,1	49,9	31,0µV	105µV
6 L-2	19,6	47,9	49,7µV	274µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4056, CATHYROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:19:02
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	20,4	47,7	72,2µV	192µV
6 L-2	20,4	47,7	102µV	300µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4077 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:33:24
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	46,0	309µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	47,0	267µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4077 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:33:24
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.
 Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	46,0	121µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	47,9	105µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4077 PHOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:16:50
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	24,0	40,6	43,4µV	211µV
5 R-1	22,5	49,9	61,0µV	350µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	15,2	41,6	40,8µV	210µV
6 L-2	20,5	51,9	80,4µV	340µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4077 SCOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:03:16
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	21,1	56,4	124µV	301µV
6 L-2	21,9	54,0	134µV	299µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4081, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:16:00
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	41,1	109µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	41,1	227µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4081, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 02:16:00 Sex/Age: female/0
 ID: Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	40,1	43,9µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	38,2	109µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4081, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:59:09
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:

photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	19,1	45,5	10,1µV	63,2µV
5 R-1	18,6	45,0	27,9µV	156µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	18,1	43,5	30,1µV	112µV
6 L-2	20,5	45,5	49,6µV	247µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4081, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:43:00
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	18,0	46,2	58,6µV	175µV
6 L-2	18,8	46,2	103µV	274µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4090 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:05:33
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	48,9	224µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	47,9	179µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4090 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:05:33
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	49,9	113µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	49,9	95,2µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4090 PHOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:48:29
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	25,0	48,4	28,1µV	136µV
5 R-1	23,5	53,3	52,0µV	254µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	21,5	47,9	17,9µV	121µV
6 L-2	21,0	53,3	47,6µV	206µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4090 SCOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 05:36:21
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	14,9	56,4	106µV	220µV
6 L-2	15,7	57,9	91,0µV	174µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4092, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:32:43
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	46,0	245µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	45,0	376µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4092, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:32:43
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	46,0	100µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	47,0	228µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4092 PHOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:15:58
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	24,0	47,9	29,3µV	134µV
5 R-1	22,0	49,9	48,2µV	299µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	21,5	47,5	16,5µV	188µV
6 L-2	22,0	49,9	61,6µV	357µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4092 SCOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 06:07:10
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	21,9	54,0	88,3µV	217µV
6 L-2	22,7	54,0	104µV	274µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4094 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:36:05
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	45,0	160µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	45,0	241µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4094 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:36:05
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	45,0	49,2µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	45,0	113µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4094 PHOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:18:59
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	23,0	49,9	27,1µV	105µV
5 R-1	22,0	49,4	42,8µV	224µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	14,7	46,5	45,8µV	155µV
6 L-2	21,0	49,4	60,9µV	252µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4094 SCOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:05:44
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	17,2	50,1	87,3µV	236µV
6 L-2	18,0	49,3	96,6µV	220µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4095 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:06:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	47,0	249µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	49,9	113µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4095 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:06:23
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	47,0	93,8µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	45,0	41,4µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4095 PHOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:50:44
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: female/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	24,0	52,3	19,7µV	164µV
5 R-1	21,0	52,8	59,1µV	303µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	21,5	55,3	3,36µV	94,4µV
6 L-2	19,6	52,3	47,1µV	195µV

Patient: **PSAMLE15WEEKS 4095 SCOTOPIC, CATHY ROCHE, 15/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:38:16
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	21,9	57,1	98,4µV	229µV
6 L-2	24,3	61,1	47,1µV	127µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4117 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 04:59:59
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	47,0	359µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	46,0	355µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4117 FLICKER, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 04:59:59
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	47,0	188µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	46,0	209µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4117, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 04:43:03
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	15,2	47,5	31,2µV	242µV
5 R-1	22,5	52,3	59,4µV	354µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	18,6	46,5	36,6µV	232µV
6 L-2	22,0	51,9	56,6µV	354µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4117, CATHY ROCHE, 14/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 03:05:12
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	14,9	51,7	131µV	331µV
6 L-2	17,2	52,4	136µV	343µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4123, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:40:30
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	43,1	131µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	43,1	248µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4123, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:40:30
 ID:

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	40,1	65,9µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	41,1	142µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4123, CATHYROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 01:21:55
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	15,7	43,5	11,2µV	61,2µV
5 R-1	20,1	46,0	35,0µV	143µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	19,6	42,6	34,1µV	131µV
6 L-2	18,1	46,5	63,0µV	258µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4123, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:59:49
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	13,3	45,4	74,6µV	207µV
6 L-2	14,1	46,2	95,0µV	265µV

Patient: psamLE15WEEKS 4172, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:57:46
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1	45,0	151µV
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1		
2 L-2	47,0	179µV
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2		

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4172, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:57:46
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

photopic Flicker

Channel	P1 [ms]	N1-P1
1 R-1		
3 R-1		
5 R-1		
7 R-1	47,9	44,5µV
2 L-2		
4 L-2		
6 L-2		
8 L-2	49,9	77,0µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 4172, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:41:15
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Diagnosis:
photopic single flash 2

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
3 R-1	19,6	47,0	11,5µV	97,2µV
5 R-1	22,5	49,9	37,9µV	202µV
2 L-2				
4 L-2	19,6	47,9	17,5µV	118µV
6 L-2	22,5	52,3	40,3µV	218µV

Patient: **psamLE15WEEKS 7172, CATHY ROCHE, 19/10/2020**
 Examined: 01/01/2009 00:07:07
 ID:

Electrode: DTL Thread
 Pupil Size: nondil.

Sex/Age: male/0
 Operator:

Diagnosis:
scotopic single flash 3

Channel	a [ms]	b [ms]	a-wave	b-wave
1 R-1				
2 L-2				
3 R-1				
4 L-2				
5 R-1	22,7	54,8	73,1µV	148µV
6 L-2	20,4	54,0	113µV	225µV